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Validation and application of an IC-ESI-MS method for low-weight cations, for the chemical profiling of inorganic explosives and pyrotechnics.

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Abstract

Fireworks are a serious topic of discussion in the Netherlands. The misuse of fireworks is a big issue in the country that has to be reduced and eventually stopped. In an attempt to help the police in this case, the NFI set out on the development of a new method by IC-ESI-MS for the identification and quantification of 18 low-weight cations for the chemical profiling of inorganic explosives and pyrotechnics. The aim of this study is to validate and apply this new method for the profiling of inorganic explosives and pyrotechnics. The LOD, LOQ, working range and linearity have been studied as part of the validation. The results show an LOD as low as 1 ppb and a correlation coefficient of > 0.995 . In addition, the validated method was applied to a set of eight different commercial fireworks have been studied for their cationic composition in three stages: intact, post explosion and after burning. Up to four cationic profiles of the fuses, six cationic profiles of the powders and five cationic profiles of the post blast residues have been set up. Based on the cationic profile of each item, we might be able to individualize samples.

Abbreviation List

IC	Ion Chromatography
ESI	Electron Spray Ionization
MS	Mass Spectrometry
NFI	Netherlands Forensic Institute
LOD	Limit of Detection
LOQ	Limit of Quantification
UV	Ultraviolet
S/N	Signal/Noise
2G	Second Generation
PS5	Petard Shark 5 grams
TP12	Testy Petard 12 grams
HN	Hot-Needle

1. Introduction

The use of fireworks and New Year's Eve are inevitably linked in the Netherlands, a worldwide known tradition taken from China. Fireworks are a serious topic of discussion every year. Municipalities are increasingly setting up firework free zones during New Year's Eve. Misuse can cause tragic events and injuries. Aside from the personal danger, there is a huge risk of fire and property damage. These troubles caused by accidents and vandalism have led to the government taking action in limiting the use of fireworks. Strict rules have been made for the use of fireworks. Besides accidental misuses of fireworks, there is also criminal misuse. Illegal trading in fireworks is mostly run by Dutch drug criminals, according to Ad Nieuwdorp, a firework specialist working for the police. Since 2017, a number of detectives have been investigating the trade in illegal fireworks throughout the year in the Netherlands. Large surveys are run on these criminal "firework gangs" by the police.^{1,2}

Forensic identification of inorganic explosives, such as pyrotechnics, can provide essential evidence for court in a casework investigation.³ The pyrotechnic items that are received by the NFI for investigation, are commercial fireworks. The following items are just a small example of the set of fireworks the NFI receives for casework investigation. The commercial names of the studied fireworks are: *Spanish Cracker XL*, *Bazooka's*, *Shark PS5*, *Dum Bum*, *Crazy Robots*, *Match Cracker TP12*, *Cobra 6 Super* and *Cobra 6 2G*. The pyrotechnics of concern can be divided into two groups; legal and illegal. The first two items are black powder based and considered legal, and the other six items are flash powder based and are considered illegal by the police in the Netherlands.

The pyrotechnics of interest are black and flash powder based fireworks. A firework item consists of different parts; a fuse, protective paper, clay choke (depending on the item), a tube and a clay plug. **Figure 1** displays a cross section of a firework item. Depending on the kind of firework and its purpose, the tube can be filled with either black powder, flash powder or both.

Figure 1. A schematic cross section of a firework item.⁴

Black powder is an explosive composition and can be used for pyrotechnical purposes. It is classified as a low explosive, because its decomposition rate and effect are slow. Black powder is described as a cheap and stable pyrotechnic powder. It consists of three basic compounds; potassium nitrate (KNO₃), charcoal (C) and sulfur (S). Black powder exists in different ratios of these compounds. The KNO₃ supplies oxygen for the reaction, C provides fuel in the form of carbon and S serves as fuel and binder in this kind of powder.^{5,6} The chemical equation of the combustion of black powder is:

Flash powder is a commonly known pyrotechnic powder. It is an explosive mixture of oxidizers and metallic fuel which burns extremely quick. Flash powders can be made of different compositions, most common are potassium perchlorate (KClO₄), and the metallic fuel used can be aluminum (Al) or magnesium (Mg) and sulfur (S). Flash powder is one of the most unstable pyrotechnic compositions.⁷ The chemical equation of the combustion of flash powder is:

Depending on the firework item, the pyrotechnic compositions can consist of different compounds which serve for different purposes. These compounds aid in providing special effects like, bright colors, sparkles, smoke and glitter effects. Additionally, some act as oxidizer, fuel or stabilizer. The following cations that have been studied in this research can be found in the chosen firework items. To give an idea on why these cations are studied a list of their purpose is shown below;

Aluminum – Aluminum is used to produce sparkles, silver and white flames. Aluminum is also used as the metallic fuel in items that contain flash powders.

Barium – Barium is used to create green effects; it aids in steadying other hazardous chemicals and stabilizes volatile components.

Calcium – Calcium is used for the saturation of colors; calcium salts produce orange effects.

Copper – Copper creates blue and green effects.

Lithium – Lithium is a metal that is used to red effects; a commonly used colorant.

Magnesium – Magnesium produces bright white effects and used as metallic fuel in items that contain flash powders.

Potassium – Potassium aids in the oxidization of the powders present in the items; it is one of the main components present.

Strontium – Strontium creates red effects and is used for stabilization of the pyrotechnic compositions.

Sodium – Sodium creates a golden yellow effect.

Zinc – Zinc is used for creating smoke effects.^{5,8,9,10}

For the identification of inorganic explosives and pyrotechnics, the items of interest are studied for their ionic composition. The NFI's Explosive and Explosions team does research on the determination of ions in inorganic explosives with the use of ion chromatography (IC). Ion Chromatography is a widely used technique for the analysis of inorganic explosives in forensic laboratories. The team has been using the method QOL00863.¹¹ This method is able to identify up to eight cations and eight anions. The method is applied by an IC coupled to a conductivity

detector and a UV-detector. This method only gives a qualitative indication of the ions, because of its low selectivity and specificity.

The chemical profiling of inorganic explosives is very challenging, and the current existing methods are not suitable for this study. The current IC methods lack selectivity and sensitivity for low-weight ionic species in complex matrices. To face this challenge in this study, the IC is coupled to a mass spectrometer (MS) detector. The MS is able to determine and quantify up to 18 cations at low concentration levels.

Although there are papers published on methods by Ion Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (IC-MS) in the forensic field, the methods do not describe the use of IC-MS for the chemical profiling of inorganic explosives.^{12-17,21}

In an attempt to help the police in reducing the production and distribution of illegal fireworks and to link fireworks that are used in criminal acts, the Explosion and Explosives team of the Netherlands Forensic Institute (NFI) set out on the development of a method for the chemical profiling of inorganic explosives and pyrotechnics.

The aim of this study is to validate and apply a new method by IC-ESI-MS for the identification and quantification of 18 low-weight cations for the chemical profiling of inorganic explosives and pyrotechnics.

2. Experimental

2.1 Material and Chemicals

The inorganic salts (see **Table 1**) were purchased from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany).

Acetonitrile was purchased from Bisolve BV (Valkenswaard, The Netherlands) and oxalic acid from Sigma-Aldrich (Zwijndrecht, The Netherlands). All reagents used throughout the validation and sample analysis are of analytical grade ($\geq 98\%$). Alcohol swabs used for the experiments were purchased from B. Braun Medical BV (Oss, The Netherlands). The 0.45 μm filters, ceramic incinerating dishes and pp syringes were purchased from VWR (The Netherlands). The buckets and foam were provided by the NFI (The Hague, The Netherlands).

Table 1. The following 18 cations of interest were validated for the method.

Analyte	Formula	Obtained from
Lithium	Li^+	Lithium nitrate
Sodium	Na^+	Sodium chloride
Potassium	K^+	Potassium nitrate
Cesium	Cs^+	Cesium nitrate
Ammonium	NH_4^+	Ammonium nitrate
Ethylammonium	$\text{C}_2\text{H}_5\text{N}^+$	Ethylammonium chloride
Dicyandiamide	$\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{N}_4^+$	Dicyandiamide
Magnesium	Mg^{2+}	Magnesium nitrate hexahydrate
Calcium	Ca^{2+}	Calcium sulfate dihydrate
Strontium	Sr^{2+}	Strontium nitrate
Barium	Ba^{2+}	Barium nitrate
Manganese	Mn^{2+}	Manganese (II) sulfate monohydrate
Cobalt	Co^{2+}	Cobalt (II) chloride
Copper	Cu^{2+}	Copper (II) chloride
Zinc	Zn^{2+}	Zinc chloride
Cadmium	Cd^{2+}	Cadmium chloride hydrate
Aluminum	Al^{3+}	Aluminum sulfate hydrate
Lead	Pb^{2+}	Lead (II) chloride

2.2 Analytical Instrument

A Metrohm 850 Professional IC equipped with a Metrosep C Supp 1 cation-exchange column (250 x 4.0 mm) and a Metrohm 919 IC Autosampler Plus was used. The IC system was coupled to a Waters® SQ Detector 2, equipped with a single quadrupole with an ESI Z-Spray as ion source (see **Figure 2**). Additionally, a Waters® UPLC ACQUITY high pressure pump was used for an automatic post-column rinsing of the MS interphase.

Figure 2. A schematic representation of the IC-ESI-MS system.

2.3 Analytical Method

Depending on the cation, a 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ or 10000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ aqueous stock solution was prepared. In addition, based on these individual stock solutions, a complex standard solution containing all the cations was prepared at 2.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 20 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. Daily, a calibration series ranging from 0.1 to 15 mg/L, was prepared out of the 2.0 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and 20 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ complex standard solutions before each analysis of the samples. The mobile phase was prepared with 75% ultrapure water, 25%

acetonitrile and 4.9 mM oxalic acid. The IC was used in isocratic mode at a constant flow of 1.0 mL/min and a column temperature of 30 °C. Firstly, the system was flushed for 10 minutes with a high-pressure pump at a flow rate of 0.8 mL/min. Once the pressure was stable, around 12.0 MPa, the flow was increased to 1.0 mL/min. The mobile phase was led through a piece of tubing connected to a T-split that splits the eluent for 30% to the MS and 70% to the waste.

The MS instrument was operated in positive ESI mode. The MS was running on the following conditions: 1kV capillary voltage; 350 °C desolvation temperature; 1200 L/Hr desolvation gas flow; 150 °C ion source temperature. The specific cone voltages for the MS for each analyte are displayed in **Table 16, Appendix 1**.

2.3.1 Sample Preparation

The extraction method (i.e. NFI SOP 161501)¹⁸ used for the preparation of the samples consisted of adding 10 mL of ultrapure water. This step was followed by sonication of the sample for 10 minutes and was then filtered through a syringe attached to a 0.45 µm filter.

2.4 Validation Experiments

For the validation of the method, the 18 cations of interest were obtained from their complementary inorganic salts (**Table 1**). The following validation experiments will be discussed in this study; LOD and LOQ and the working range.

2.4.1 LOD and LOQ

The detection limit of the instrument (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) were measured for each analyte (i.e. cation). The complex standard solutions were prepared at concentrations according to the expected LOD. Each complex standard solution was prepared 10 times and analyzed once. The background noise of the detector during a single separation was compared to

the obtained signals from the complex standard solution containing concentrations of the 18 different analytes.

2.4.2 Linearity and Working Range

The instrument working range in the MS detector was assessed by analyzing a calibration series of the complex standard ranging from the lower and upper ends of the predicted working range of each cation. Each sample was prepared three times. After the analysis of the first set, the plotting of the obtained data gave a visual confirmation of the linear range and of the upper and lower limits of the instrument working range. After, the two other sets were analyzed, and the regression statistics and residual plots were studied to confirm the relationship between the concentration and the instrument response.

2.5 Data Acquisition

Metrohm's MagIC Net 3.1 combined with Waters's MassLynx™ 4.1 and TargetLynx™ 4.1 was used for the acquisition of the data obtained after each analysis.

2.6 Application of the Method

The method was applied for the chemical profiling of flash and black powder based firework items post explosion. The sample set consisted of eight different commercial fireworks provided by the NFI. A list of the commercial fireworks of interest is shown in **Table 2**. All pyrotechnic compositions were analyzed with IC-ESI-MS in three stages: intact (pre-blast), after burning (hot-needle test) and post-explosive (post-blast). In addition, the composition of the fuses, intact and after burning, was also analyzed.

Table 2. The commercial names and pictured of the fireworks studied for their chemical profiling.

Firework	Picture	Powder
Spanish Cracker XL		Black powder
Bazooka's		Black powder
Shark PS5		Flash powder
Dum Bum		Flash powder
Crazy Robots		Flash powder
Match Cracker TP 12		Flash powder
Cobra 6 Super		Black and Flash powder
Cobra 6 2G		Flash powder

2.6.1 Post-Blast Residue Study

The post-blast residues were collected after explosion of the items at a test location in Soesterberg, The Netherlands. The experiment was carried out by using a bucket with a lid. In the lid a hole was drilled, and the fuse of the desired firework connected to a safety fuse was pulled through the hole (**Figure 3**). The bucket was then wrapped with foam and placed in a steal cylinder with sand in the bottom. After the explosion, the collection of the residues was carried out by sampling the lid, upper, lower and bottom part of the bucket with an alcohol swab. The

swab was then put in a plastic jar. Of each firework, three items were exploded. The samples were extracted according to the sample preparation protocol.

Figure 3. Design of the bucket used for the post-blast residue study.

2.6.2 Pre-Blast Study

The set of eight intact fireworks were separately disassembled under the most restricted safety measurements of the NFI. Each item came in a set of three. The item was opened with a scalpel and the flash or black powder, depending on the item, was collected in small vials. Before the analysis, 25 mg of the powder was extracted according the sample preparation protocol.¹⁷ The powder in the items was sampled three times, in the cleanest way possible to avoid any contamination from other parts of the item. The fuse of each item was cut into small pieces and the powder inside was obtained. This powder was then extracted and analyzed.

Figure 4 displays an example of the firework item, Dum Bum, which contains flash powder.

Figure 4. Dum Bum, a flash powder firework item (a) before (b) after disassembling.

Figure 5 displays an example of a firework item, Spanish Cracker XL, that contains black powder, before and after disassembling.

Figure 5. Spanish Cracker XL, a black powder firework item, (a) before (b) after disassembling.

2.6.3 Hot-Needle Test

For the analysis of the pyrotechnic residues after burning, hot-needle tests were performed. The items of interest are similar to the items used for the post-blast residue experiment. Amounts of 25 mg of flash powder or black powder, depending on the item, were sampled three times. The hot-needle test was carried out by heating a needle with a Bunsen burner (**Figure 6a**) and place it on the small amount of the black or flash powder in an incinerating dish (**Figure 6b**), after the combustion took place the residues were collected with alcohol swabs. The samples were extracted according to the sample preparation protocol.

Figure 6. (a) Intact powder before combustion (b) the hot needle is placed over the powder (c) powder after combustion.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Validation

One of the aims of this study was to validate the IC-ESI-MS method for the analysis of cations.

This validation is carried out in order to demonstrate if the performance of the method is adequate for the use of this particular forensic purpose.

Due to the fact that the internship started in the middle of the validation process, the experimental part of the validation experiments was missed. The validation of this particular method started in January 2019 and is still not finished. The accuracy, the method LOD and LOQ and a major part of the reproducibility and robustness experiments have been carried out by the team. I have only been part of the data analysis of the instrumental LOD and LOQ and the working range. During this time, I have learned how to run the method, how to interpret the data and how to prepare the samples for analysis. Due to lack of time failed experiments and the remaining experiments of the validation cannot be performed and studied. With the obtained information about the method from the performed validation experiments, we decided that the method was sufficient enough to apply it to real samples. We trust on the results obtained by this method.

For the validation experiments a set of 18 cations were validated; lithium, sodium, potassium, cesium, ammonium, ethylammonium, dicyandiamide, magnesium, calcium, strontium, barium, manganese, cobalt, copper, zinc, cadmium, aluminum and lead. The performance characteristics were evaluated according to the guidelines proposed by Eurachem.^{19,20}

3.1.1 LOD and LOQ

The instrumental LOD and LOQ of the MS detector were measured for each cation. A positive result was considered when each analyte was identified in all the ten independent samples. The

measuring strategy used was Signal-to-Noise (S/N) ratio, considering a detected peak when S/N is over 3, and a quantifiable peak when S/N is over 10. Other parameters such as retention time and peak shape were also taken into count to make this result valid.

The determination of the LOD and LOQ for cesium is taken as an example to show how the LOD and LOQ are calculated for all cations. **Figure 7** shows one of the MS chromatograms obtained during the experiment. The x-axis shows the retention time (min) and the y-axis the intensity (%).

Figure 7. One of the obtained MS chromatograms for cesium at a concentration of 1ppb.

The corresponding concentration in the chromatogram is then converted to a concentration that corresponds to $S/N = 3$. For a concentration of $0.001 \mu\text{g/mL}$ (i.e. 1 ppb) for cesium, the area is 10756 au and the noise is 1537 au. The S/N is 7. So, for $S/N = 3$, we obtain an absolute concentration of $0.0023 \mu\text{g/mL}$ for the LOD of cesium. For the determination of the LOQ a $S/N= 10$ is considered. Hence, for $S/N = 10$, we obtain an absolute concentration of $0.007 \mu\text{g/mL}$ for the LOQ of cesium. The experiment was carried out for the 18 cations and the result is shown in **Table 3**.

The expected LOD and LOQ values were compared to the validated values. For Mg^{2+} , Sr^{2+} and Al^{2+} the expected LOD meets the validated value. The results showed instrument limits below 1 ppb, and in particular very low detection limits and very low quantification limits for the ions; Li^+ , Na^+ and K^+ . The validated values for Cs^+ , NH_4^+ , $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{N}^+$, Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Pb^{2+} do not meet the expected values for the LOD and LOQ. These cations could be detected below the expected LOD, but because of the peak shape their final instrument limit is higher than expected. This was probably influenced by the performance of the MS, which has not been working in the best condition at times. Changes in the column and the mobile phase can also have an effect on the results.

Table 3. Expected and validated instrument LOD and LOQ values for the analytes of interest.

Analyte	Expected LOD ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Validated LOD ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Expected LOQ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Validated LOQ ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)
Li^+	0.001	0.0005	0.005	0.0006
Na^+	0.001	0.0009	0.008	0.0011
K^+	0.001	0.0005	0.010	0.0008
Cs^+	0.001	0.0025	0.008	0.004
NH_4^+	0.05	0.250	0.100	0.350
$\text{C}_2\text{H}_8\text{N}^+$	0.005	0.300	0.008	0.040
$\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{N}^+$	0.005	0.120	0.008	0.015
Mg^{2+}	0.005	0.005	0.010	0.015
Ca^{2+}	0.001	0.050	0.030	0.060
Sr^{2+}	0.080	0.080	0.080	0.200
Ba^{2+}	0.080	0.600	0.500	0.800
Mn^{2+}	0.005	0.025	0.050	0.037

Co²⁺	0.005	0.012	0.010	0.050
Cu²⁺	0.030	0.075	0.500	0.120
Zn²⁺	0.050	0.250	0.070	0.300
Cd²⁺	0.050	0.275	0.050	0.375
Al²⁺	0.080	0.080	0.100	0.200
Pb²⁺	0.080	0.400	0.100	0.700

3.1.2 Linearity and Working Range

The working range is expected to range from the LOQ of each analyte to a maximum of around 30 µg/mL (ppm) for some cations. Each cation was identified by analyzing their complementary species at different cone voltages in SIR mode. All ions were measured as +1. One of the MS chromatogram obtained during the validation experiment is shown in **Figure 8**.

Figure 8. One of the MS chromatogram obtained of the 8 µg/mL standard from the calibration series. (x) retention time (y) intensity/signal of the mass detector.

Firstly, the linearity was visually tested for outliers in the residuals plot. **Figure 9a** displays an example of a result that meets the expected linearity specifications for this particular validation experiment. The data points in the scatter plot show a linear relation, the residual plot does not show a pattern but is rather random and this also indicates a linear relation between the concentration and the instrument response. To confirm the linearity a “lack of fit” (LOF) test has been carried out. The test shows that the null hypothesis (H_0) cannot be rejected if $P > \alpha$ (H_0 = there is no lack of fit; $\alpha = 0.05$). According to the predefined validation specification for the correlation coefficient should be of $R^2 \geq 0.995$. This value is required for forensic purposes; in this field the highest certainty is required.

Figure 9a. Results of the linearity experiment for cesium with $y = 2E+06(\pm 349414) x + 48578(\pm 83941)$ $s_{y/x} = 240006$; $R^2 = 0.9991$. (1) Residuals plot and (2) scatter plot.

Figure 9b shows an example of a result that does not meet the expected linearity specification.

The results for potassium show the opposite of what has been discussed for cesium. This result is related to the fact that the standard solution was prepared in a glass volumetric flask. The result of the blank show a high signal of potassium. Due to lack of time, this experiment could not be repeated for this specific cation.

Figure 9b. Results of the linearity experiment for potassium with $y = -2546,4(\pm 23349) x + 80160(\pm 11315)$ $s_{y/x} = 10920$; $R^2 = 0.146$. (1) Residuals plot and (2) scatter plot.

Table 4 displays the expected and validated working range for the 18 cations. As expected in ESI interphases, it was observed that the working range depends on the analyte. Most of the ions show a linear response, except for Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Al^{2+} . The correlation coefficient is of $R^2 \geq 0.995$ for most of the ions, which is satisfactory. All cations showed narrower linear working ranges than expected. Cs^+ , $\text{C}_2\text{H}_8\text{N}^+$, $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{N}_4^+$, Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Pb^{2+} show a slightly wider quadratic range, still with $R^2 \geq 0.995$.

Table 4. The 18 cations and their corresponding expected intervals including the expected LOQ and the upper end of the working range.

Cation	Expected Interval ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	Working Range ($\mu\text{g/mL}$)	R²	Linear/ Quadratic
Li⁺	0.005 - 1	0.0006 – 1	0.9998	Linear
Na⁺	0.008 - 1	0.0011 – 2	0.9894*	Linear
K⁺	0.01 - 5	*	*	*
Cs⁺	0.008 - 20	0.004 – 8	0.9991	Linear
		0.004 – 15	0.9986	Quadratic
NH₄⁺	0.1 - 8	0.350 – 1	0.9972	Linear
C₂H₈N⁺	0.008 - 2	0.040 – 1	0.9997	Linear
		0.040 – 10	0.9904	Quadratic
C₂H₄N₄⁺	0.008 - 20	0.015 – 4	0.9938	Linear
		0.015 – 8	0.9998	Quadratic
Mg²⁺	0.01 - 15	0.015 – 4	0.9984	Linear
Ca²⁺	0.03 - 20	0.02 – 6	0.9993	Linear
		0.060 – 12.5	0.9979	Quadratic
Sr²⁺	0.08 - 30	0.200 – 6	0.9976	Linear
Ba²⁺	0.5 - 25	0.800 – 10	0.9937	Linear
		0.800 – 15	0.9952	Quadratic
Mn²⁺	0.05 - 20	0.037 – 4	0.9926	Linear
		0.037 – 10	0.9955	Quadratic
Co²⁺	0.01 - 30	0.050 – 10	0.998	Linear
		0.050 – 15	0.9964	Quadratic
Cu²⁺	0.5 - 25	0.120 – 12.5	0.9991	Quadratic
Zn²⁺	0.07 - 25	0.300 – 8	0.9955	Quadratic
Cd²⁺	0.05 - 30	0.375 – 8	0.9956	Linear
		0.375 – 15	0.9962	Quadratic
Al²⁺	0.1 - 25	0.200 – 12.5	0.9995	Quadratic

Pb²⁺	0.1 - 20	0.700 – 8	0.990	Linear
		0.700 – 15	0.9955	Quadratic

*due to lack of time this failed experiment could not be repeated.

3.2 Application to the chemical profiling of inorganic explosives and pyrotechnics

The second aim of this study was to apply the validated method to pyrotechnic samples: the powders and fuses originated from the commercial firework items of interest. To avoid any contamination from the clay and the tube, although very challenging, we tried to obtain the powders in the cleanest way possible. The fuses were in direct contact with the powder, this type of contamination could not be avoided. The possibility of the cations originating from the bucket, foam, cylinder and sand is discarded since blanks of these matrices were taken prior to the experiment. The powders and fuses were analyzed in three different stages; intact, after burning and post explosion. Each item will be discussed separately.

Spanish Cracker XL

As seen in **Table 5**, potassium was detected in all three stages. Potassium cation is part of the main component and oxidizer, it is probably present in the form of potassium nitrate. Besides potassium, ammonium was detected in post explosion residues. This cation might originate from the fuse, tube, clay, protective paper, ink or from other reactions. Burnt residues of the fuse show the presence of zinc. Zinc compounds are often used to create smoke effects. It is unknown to why this cation was not detected in the intact fuse.

Table 5. Cations detected in the Spanish Cracker XL intact, post-explosion and after burning.

Spanish Cracker XL	K⁺	NH₄⁺	Zn²⁺
Intact Powder			
Intact Fuse			
Post Explosion			
HN Powder			
HN Fuse			

Bazooka's

Potassium was detected in all three stages. Potassium is probably present in the form of potassium nitrate, which serves as the main oxidizer in black powder. As seen in **Table 6**, *Bazooka's* show that ammonium is detected in the intact powder and post-explosion. The presence of this cation in the powder is confirmed by analysis of the burnt residues of the powder. Copper was detected in the intact powder, fuse and post explosion. Copper was only detected in two out of the three fuses. This result does not confirm that copper is always present in the fuse. The fuse sticks out and is exposed to contamination from the environment and packaging and it is also in direct contact with the powder. Copper is used as an oxidizer besides creating blue effects.²³ The presence of ammonium in the intact powder might be related to the fact that it is used as ammonium perchlorate to give an intense blue color in combination with copper in the form of copper carbonate.²² Manganese is only detected in post explosion residues, this means that this cation could originate from the fuse, tube, clay, protective paper, ink or the environment of the test location, and not solely from the powder or fuse. Zinc was detected in the powder and fuse after burning. As in the previous item, zinc appears again and there is not a direct link to other result.

Table 6. *Cations detected in the Bazooka's item: intact, post explosion and after burning.*

Bazooka's	K⁺	NH₄⁺	Zn²⁺	Cu²⁺	Mn²⁺
Intact Powder					
Intact Fuse				*	
Post Explosion					
HN Powder			*		
HN Fuse					

**Copper was detected in two out of three intact fuses. *Zinc was detected in one out of three.*

Shark PS5

This item is a flash powder based firework. As seen in **Table 7**, the potassium cation is part of the main component and oxidizer, it is probably present in the form of potassium perchlorate in this type of pyrotechnic composition. Post-blast study of *Shark PS5* shows the cesium cation, which is quite uncommon in pyrotechnic compositions of this kind. Cesium was not detected in any of the previous analyses. Cesium might probably originate from the fuse, tube, clay, protective paper, ink or a reaction. Aluminum was detected in the intact powder but not in post explosion residues. The presence of aluminum in the powder was confirmed by the hot-needle test. It is also true that aluminum was detected in one out of the three items of the *Shark* in the hot-needle experiment. Due to the fact that aluminum is present as flakes in flash powder and therefore not soluble in water, in some cases it could not be detected. This result could also be related to the fact that the cation could not be identified because of the LOD. We only sampled a part of the bucket. Aluminum serves as the main metal fuel in flash powder. Barium was only detected in the intact powder. Ammonium was only detected post-explosion; this is seen by the rest of the items as well. This cation might originate from the swab that was used for sampling. The swabs contain urea that might react with the warm remains of the explosion and the rest of the chemicals.²⁵ Manganese was detected in all three stages except in the burnt residues of the fuse. The reasoning behind this is yet unknown. Zinc was detected in the fuse after burning. Zinc was not detected in the other analyses done. This result is also seen in the previous items, Zinc might come from the paperclip, scissors, ceramic incinerating dish or the dirty fume hood. Copper was only detected in the intact fuse of this item; other analyses do not show the presence of this cation. This result might be related to the fact that the fuse sticks out and is exposed to

contamination from the environment and its packaging, that it is simply part of the fuse or it is present in concentrations below the LOD.

Table 7. Cations detected in Shark PS5: intact, post explosion and after burning.

Shark PS5	K⁺	Cs⁺	Al²⁺	Ba²⁺	NH₄⁺	Mn²⁺	Zn²⁺	Cu²⁺
Intact Powder								
Intact Fuse								
Post Explosion								
HN Powder			*					
HN Fuse								

*Aluminum was detected in two out of three items.

Dum Bum

Table 8 shows the results of this specific item in the three analyzed stages. The potassium cation is part of the main component and oxidizer, it is probably present in the form of potassium perchlorate. Ammonium was only detected post-explosion and in the burnt residues of the fuse, this is seen by the rest of the items as well. As mentioned before, this cation might originate from the urea in the swab that was used for sampling. Zinc was detected in the fuse after burning. Zinc was not detected in the other analyses done. This result supports our suspicions about that zinc might come from the paperclip, dirty fume hood. Copper was appeared in the intact fuse of this item; other analyses do not show the presence of this cation. This result might be related to contamination coming from the surroundings of the fuse, like its packaging.

As in all the other cases, zinc was detected in the fuse after burning and not detected in the other analyses. Manganese was detected in all three stages except in the burnt residues of the fuse. An explanation for this is still unknown. The intact powder and post explosion of the item show the presence of barium. This is the first item that shows barium post explosion. Barium aids in

steadying other hazardous chemicals and stabilizes volatile components in pyrotechnic compositions. Barium in barium carbonate or barium nitrate, produces a green flame in a composition that contains ammonium perchlorate as the oxidizer.²⁴ Aluminum was detected in the intact powder and in the burnt residues of the powder. Aluminum was detected in only two out of the three items in the hot-needle experiment. Due to the fact that aluminum is present as flakes in flash powder and therefore not soluble in water, in some cases it could not be detected. This result could also be related to the LOD of aluminum. Post-blast study of *Dum Bum* shows that the presence of strontium is quite uncommon. Strontium was only detected post-explosion and not in any of the other analyses done. An explanation for this outcome is yet unknown.

Table 8. Cations detected in Dum Bum: intact, post explosion and after burning.

Dum Bum	K⁺	NH₄⁺	Zn²⁺	Cu²⁺	Mn²⁺	Ba²⁺	Al²⁺	Sr²⁺
Intact Powder								
Intact Fuse								
Post Explosion								
HN Powder							*	
HN Fuse								

*Aluminum was detected in two out of the three items.

Crazy Robots

Potassium was detected in all three stages. This trend is seen in all previous items as well. This firework is flash powder based. The main oxidizer in this type of powder is potassium perchlorate, and that is where the potassium cation is originating from. Ammonium was only detected post-explosion and in the burnt residues of the fuse, this case is seen by the rest of the items as well. Its explanation is the same as for the rest of the items where ammonium is detected in post explosion residues or after burning. The burnt residues of the fuse show again the presence of zinc, this cation not detected in the other analyses done. This result confirms that

zinc is a cross contaminant from the materials used for the hot-needle test. Copper was only detected in the intact fuse of this item; other analyses do not show the presence of this cation. This was also the case for the previous item. The same explanation mentioned for the Dum Bum item applies to this one as well. Manganese was detected in all three stages except in the burnt residues of the fuse. An explanation for this is still unknown. The intact powder and post explosion of the item show the presence of barium. This is the second item that shows barium post explosion. Barium aids in steadying other hazardous chemicals and stabilizes volatile components in pyrotechnic compositions. Barium in barium carbonate or nitrate produces a green flame in a composition that contains ammonium or potassium perchlorate as the oxidizer.²⁴ As seen in some of the other flash powder items, aluminum was detected in the intact powder and in the burnt residues of the powder. Aluminum was detected in only two out of the three items in the hot-needle experiment. Flash powder contains aluminum that serves as fuel. The reason to why aluminum is not always detected or identified is explained previously. As shown in **Table 9** strontium was detected in the intact fuse and post-explosion. Strontium was only detected in two out of three intact fuses and in one out of the three fuses in the hot-needle test. However, the detection of strontium in the intact fuse, post explosion and burnt residues confirms its presence in the fuse of *Crazy Robots*.

Table 9. Cations detected in Crazy Robots: intact, post explosion and after burning.

Crazy Robots	K⁺	NH₄⁺	Zn²⁺	Cu²⁺	Mn²⁺	Ba²⁺	Al²⁺	Sr²⁺
Intact Powder							*	
Intact Fuse								
Post Explosion								
HN Powder								
HN Fuse								

*Aluminum was detected in two out of the three items.

Match Cracker PT12

Table 10 shows the results obtained from the experiments done on the *Match Cracker PT12*.

Potassium was detected in all three stages. This trend is seen in all previous items as well. As stated previously for all flash powder based fireworks, the main oxidizer in this type of powder is potassium perchlorate, and that is where the potassium cation is originating from. Ammonium was only detected post-explosion, this trend is seen by the rest of the items as well. An explanation for this outcome is discussed previously for all items. Zinc was detected in the intact fuse, post explosion and in the burnt residues of the fuse. Since this cation was also detected post explosion it opens a door to the possibility that the fuse of this item might contain zinc.

Manganese was detected in intact powder, in post explosion residue and in the burnt residues of the powder. Manganese in manganese oxide serves as an inorganic oxidation agent.²⁶ Aluminum was detected in the intact powder, post explosion and in the burnt residues of the powder. This specific item is a flash powder based pyrotechnic. This cation serves as the main metal fuel in flash powder.

Table 10. *Cations detected in Match Cracker PT12: intact, post explosion and after burning.*

Match Cracker PT12	K⁺	NH₄⁺	Zn²⁺	Mn²⁺	Al²⁺
Intact Powder					
Intact Fuse					
Post Explosion					
HN Powder					
HN Fuse					

Cobra 6 Super

The *Cobra 6 Super* is the only item in this set that consists of two types of powder: black and flash powder. Both powders were analyzed, and their cationic profile will be discussed below.

Table 11 shows the results obtained from the experiment done on the black powder of the item.

As seen in **table 11**, potassium was detected in all three stages. The main oxidizing compound in black powder is potassium nitrate. Ammonium was only detected post-explosion as it was seen by the rest of the items as well. The same explanation given before also applies to particular case. Copper was detected in the intact powder and post explosion. Copper in copper oxide is used as an oxidizer in pyrotechnic composition such as this type. Zinc was again detected in the fuse and powder after burning. As previously stated, zinc might be a cross contaminant from the materials used for the hot-needle test. Aluminum was only detected post explosion. This result is related to the fact that besides black powder also flash powder is present in the item. Since aluminum powder is the metal fuel in flash powder, the aluminum detected in the item post explosion is coming from the flash powder.

Table 11. *Cations detected in Cobra Super 6 black powder: intact, post explosion and after burning.*

Cobra 6 Super	K⁺	NH₄⁺	Cu²⁺	Zn²⁺	Al²⁺
Intact Powder					
Intact Fuse					
Post Explosion					
HN Powder					
HN Fuse					

Table 12 shows the results obtained from the experiment done on the flash powder of the item.

Potassium was detected in all three stages. The main oxidizing compound in flash powder is potassium perchlorate. Ammonium was detected in post explosion residues, this trend is seen by

the rest of the items as well, and the burnt residues of the powder. Zinc was only detected in the fuse after burning. This result confirms the suspicion that zinc might again be a cross contaminant from the materials used. Aluminum was detected post explosion and in the burnt residues of the powder. This specific item is a flash powder based pyrotechnic. Aluminum is not detected in other stages; this might be due to aluminum being present as flakes in the powder which are not soluble in water and therefore not present in the extract that was analyzed.

Table 12. *Cations detected in Cobra Super 6 flash powder: intact, post explosion and after burning.*

Cobra 6 Super	K⁺	NH₄⁺	Cu²⁺	Zn²⁺	Al²⁺
Intact Powder					
Intact Fuse					
Post Explosion					
HN Powder					
HN Fuse					

Cobra 6 2G

Cobra 6 2G is a flash powder based pyrotechnic. **Table 13** shows the results obtained from the experiment done on this item. The potassium cation was detected in all three stages this is due to the fact that potassium is the main component and oxidizer in this type of pyrotechnic composition. Since this item contains flash powder and the main oxidizing agent is potassium perchlorate, the potassium cation detected is part of that compound. Ammonium was only detected post-explosion this is seen in all items discussed above. Copper was detected in the intact powder, post explosion and in the burnt residues of the powder. Copper in copper oxide is used as an oxidizer in pyrotechnic compositions such as flash powder. Zinc was detected in the fuse and powder after burning. Zinc was not detected in the other analyses done. Aluminum was only detected post explosion. This result is related to the fact that besides black powder also flash

powder is present in the item. Since aluminum powder is the metal fuel in flash powder, the aluminum detected in the item post explosion is coming from the flash powder.

Table 13. *Cations detected in Cobra 2G: intact, post explosion and after burning.*

Cobra 6 2G	K⁺	NH₄⁺	Cu²⁺	Zn²⁺	Al²⁺
Intact Powder					
Intact Fuse					
Post Explosion					
HN Powder					
HN Fuse					

All these results seem to show that there are different kinds of cationic profiles. However, some of the identified cations might not be useful for this purpose. For instance, we have suspicions about zinc being a cross contaminant and we also have doubts about the presence of ammonium. Potassium is also discarded as a key marker, because it was detected in all items. In spite of that we observe different cationic profiles for the fuses, powders and post explosion residues. As shown in **table 15**, post blast study of the items shows that there are up to five different cationic profiles based on the studied items. In accordance with the obtained results for the pre blast study of the fuse, we see four different cationic profiles. Pre blast study of the powders show us six different cationic profiles. This study has allowed us to differentiate between black powder and flash powder items, through the detection of aluminum. Within the flash powder based items there are small differences (i.e. Cs⁺, Sr²⁺, Cu²⁺) which shows us a variation among this type of powder. Besides that, this study shows us that it is able to differentiate between items after explosion, five cationic profiles have been set up thanks to this study. Study of the fuses gives us extra information about cations that were not present in the powder but showed presence in post explosion residues. On the basis of the results of the studied fuses, four different cationic profiles were set up.

Table 15. The cations detected in the items intact, post-explosion and after burning.

Item	Intact Powder	Intact Fuse	Post Explosion	HN Powder	HN Fuse
Spanish Cracker XL	K ⁺	K ⁺	K ⁺ NH ₄ ⁺	K ⁺	K ⁺ Zn ²⁺
Bazooka's	K ⁺ NH ₄ ⁺ Cu ²⁺	K ⁺ Cu ²⁺	K ⁺ NH ₄ ⁺ Cu ²⁺ Mn ²⁺	NH ₄ ⁺ Zn ²⁺	K ⁺ Zn ²⁺
Shark PS5	K ⁺ Mn ²⁺ Ba ²⁺ , Al ²⁺	K ⁺ Cu ²⁺ Mn ²⁺	K ⁺ NH ₄ ⁺ Mn ²⁺ Cs ⁺	K ⁺ Mn ²⁺ Al ²⁺	K ⁺ Zn ²⁺
Dum Bum	K ⁺ Mn ²⁺ Ba ²⁺ Al ²⁺	K ⁺ Cu ²⁺ Mn ²⁺	K ⁺ NH ₄ ⁺ Ba ²⁺ Mn ²⁺ Sr ²⁺	K ⁺ Mn ²⁺ Al ²⁺	NH ₄ ⁺ K ⁺ Zn ²⁺
Crazy Robots	K ⁺ Mn ²⁺ Ba ²⁺ Al ²⁺	K ⁺ Cu ²⁺ Mn ²⁺ Sr ²⁺	K ⁺ NH ₄ ⁺ Ba ²⁺ Mn ²⁺ Sr ²⁺	K ⁺ Mn ²⁺ Al ²⁺	NH ₄ ⁺ K ⁺ Zn ²⁺ Sr ²⁺
Match Cracker PT12	K ⁺ Mn ²⁺ Al ²⁺	K ⁺ Zn ²⁺	K ⁺ NH ₄ ⁺ Mn ²⁺ Al ²⁺	K ⁺ Mn ²⁺ Al ²⁺	K ⁺ Zn ²⁺

Cobra 6 Super Black Powder	K^+	K^+	$K^+ NH_4^+ Cu^{2+}$ Al^{2+}	$K^+ NH_4^+$ Al^{2+}	$K^+ Zn^{2+}$
Flash Powder	$K^+ Cu^{2+}$	K^+	$K^+ NH_4^+ Cu^{2+}$ Al^{2+}	$K^+ Zn^{2+}$	$K^+ Zn^{2+}$
Cobra 6 2G	$K^+ Cu^{2+}$	K^+	$K^+ NH_4^+ Cu^{2+}$ Al^{2+}	$K^+ Zn^{2+}$ Cu^{2+}	$K^+ Zn^{2+}$

4. Conclusion

In this work, part of a validation of a method for the analysis of low-weight cations has been shown. As main conclusion of this part it can be mentioned that the expected LOD and LOQ values were compared to the validated values. For Mg^{2+} , Sr^{2+} and Al^{2+} the expected LOD meets the validated value. The results showed instrument limits below 1 ppb, and in particular very low detection limits and very low quantification limits for the ions; Li^+ , Na^+ and K^+ . The validated values for Cs^+ , NH_4^+ , $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{N}^+$, Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Pb^{2+} do not meet the expected values for the LOD and LOQ. These cations could be detected below the expected LOD, but because of the peak shape their final instrument limit is higher than expected. In addition, most of the ions show a linear response, except for Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} and Al^{2+} . The correlation coefficient is of $R^2 \geq 0.995$ for most of the ions. All cations showed narrower linear working ranges than expected. Cs^+ , $\text{C}_2\text{H}_8\text{N}^+$, $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{N}_4^+$, Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} , Mn^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Pb^{2+} show a quadratic range, with $R^2 \geq 0.995$.

Furthermore, in this work the method was applied to the profiling of real explosive related samples. Specifically fuses, powders and post blast residues of fireworks. In accordance with the obtained results different cationic profiles have been set up. This study shows us five different cationic profiles with the information gained from the analysis of the post blast residues. Secondly, the results of the analysis of the powders show us six different cationic profiles. Lastly, the study of the fuses shows four different cationic profiles. It can be concluded that based on the cationic profile, intact and post-explosion, the items can be identified. This result has been achieved in spite of the anionic profile of the items. A study on the anions of these items provides more information which might give the ability to set up more profiles. This would make the identification of the pyrotechnics complete.

5. Future Work

For an accurate determination of the performance characteristics of the method, a few experiments have to be repeated. For a complete chemical profile of the studied pyrotechnics an analysis of the anions present needs to be performed. The cationic profile of each item only gives half of the information that is required. I would recommend including the data obtained for the anion analysis for a complete ionic profiling of the pyrotechnics in this study.

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8. Appendix

Appendix 1:

Table 16. The specific cone voltages for the MS and m/z of the studied 18 cations.

Cation and ionic formula	Species	m/z	Cone Voltage (V)
Lithium Li^+	$[\text{2ACN}+\text{Li}]^+$	89	10
	$[\text{ACN}+\text{H}_2\text{O}+\text{Li}]^+$	66	30
	$[\text{2ACN}+\text{2H}_2\text{OH}+\text{2Li}]^+$	131	10
Sodium Na^+	$[\text{Na}]^+$	23	75/140
	$[\text{ACN}+\text{Na}]^+$	64	10
Potassium K^+	$[\text{K}]^+$	39	75/90
Cesium Cs^+	$[\text{Cs}]^+$	133	80
Ammonium NH_4^+	$[\text{NH}_4]^+$	18	10 / 30 / 50
Ethylammonium $\text{C}_2\text{H}_8\text{N}^+$	$[\text{C}_2\text{H}_7\text{N}+\text{H}]^+$	46	10/30
	$[\text{ACN}-\text{C}_2\text{H}_7\text{N}]^+$	86	10
	$[\text{ACN}-\text{CH}_3\text{N}]^+$	72	10/30/50/70/90
Dicyandiamide $\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{N}_4^+$	$[\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{N}_4+\text{H}]^+$	85	10
	$[\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{N}_4-\text{NH}_3]^+$	68	30
	$[\text{ACN}+\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{N}_4+\text{H}]^+$	126	10
Magnesium Mg^{2+}	$[\text{2ACN}+\text{5H}_2\text{O}-\text{H}+\text{Mg}]^+$	195	10
	$[\text{Mg}_2]^{2+}$	24	90
	$[\text{4H}_2\text{O}-\text{H}+\text{Mg}]^+$	95	10
	$[\text{2ACN}+\text{OH}+\text{Mg}]^+$	123	50
	$[\text{3ACN}+\text{5H}_2\text{O}-\text{H}+\text{Mg}]^+$	236	10

Calcium – Ca²⁺	$[2ACN+H_2O+Ca]^{2+}$	70	30
	$[2ACN+2H_2O+Ca]^{2+}$	79	30
	$[2ACN+3H_2O+Ca]^{2+}$	88	30
Strontium – Sr²⁺	$[H_2O-H+Sr]^+$	105	140
	$[Sr_2]^{2+}$	87/88	140
	$[Sr]^{2+}$	44	140
Barium Ba²⁺	$[Ba]^{2+}$	69	70/140
	$[ACNH+Ba]^{2+}/[ACN+Ba]^{2+}$	89.5	90
	$[H_2O-H+Ba]^+$	155	90/70
Manganese Mn²⁺	$[2ACN+ 5H_2O-H+Mn]^+$	226	30
	$[H_2O-H+Mn]^+$	71	30
	$[ACN+ H_2O-H+Mn]^+$	113	70
Cobalt Co²⁺	$[Co_2]^{2+}$	59	140
	$[4ACN+Co_2]^{2+}$	141	150
Copper Cu²⁺	$[Cu_2]^{2+}$	63	140
		65	90
Zinc Zn²⁺	$[ACN+ 5H_2O-H+^{64}Zn]^+$	194	30
	$[ACN+ H_2O-H+^{64}Zn]^+$	122	70
	$[ACN+ H_2O-H+^{66}Zn]^+$	124	70
	$[ACN+ H_2O-H+^{68}Zn]^+$	126	70
Cadmium Cd²⁺	$[^{112}Cd_2]^{2+}$	112	140
	$[^{114}Cd_2]^{2+}$	114	140
Aluminum Al³⁺	$[2H_2O-2H+Al]^+$	61	70 / 80
	$[3H_2O-2H+Al]^+$	79	70 / 80
Lead	$[^{208}Pb_2]^{2+}$	208	140

Pb²⁺	$[\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{H}+^{206}\text{Pb}]^+$	223	70 / 50
	$[\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{H}+^{208}\text{Pb}]^+$	225	70